

**Communicative Language Teaching Approach: Impact on Students’
Speaking Skills of Rural ESL Learners of Secondary Schools in
Jhargram District, West Bengal.**

Abstract

Communicative competency is an important theoretical innovation in second language (L2) instruction, especially for ESL learners. Despite broad support for CLT, many teachers lack the skills and expertise to execute it. Thus, this study tries to comprehend instructors' and students' viewpoints on CLT's application in Bengali-medium secondary schools in West Bengal to enhance students' speaking skills. It explores CLT's impacts and how to use it. This study was quasi-experimental. The study uses teacher interviews, classroom observations, pretests, and posttests for data collection. English speakers were evaluated through pre- and post-test scores, observer comments, and teacher and student assessments. Most educators and students increased their communication using CLT. Despite instructors' and students' grasp of CLT, finances and students' trouble concentrating during standardised examinations hinder its implementation. Teachers were urged to aid children with vocabulary and grammar in speaking exercises. CLT's use in classrooms to enhance pupils' communication skills will be limited. The article advises improving facilities and minimising testing to enhance students' speaking abilities.

Keywords: Communicative Language Teaching, Vocabulary, Speaking Skills.

Introduction

English is an inevitable component of modern life. English education has become a priority for governments worldwide. We can use English as a window through which we can get a view of the entire world. The current trend indicates that parents prefer to enroll their kids in English-medium schools rather than those that teach in languages like Bengali or other vernacular languages. They believe that English will protect the future of their children. However, English teaching as an L2 to children with a native language background is not an easy task in an ESL class. In the ESL classroom, numerous issues need to be resolved. Most vernacular medium schools use (GTM) English as a Second Language (ESL) approach, which can be challenging for students because it requires them to learn two languages simultaneously and to mentally translate between them during the time they speak.

The role and obligations of instructors in teaching pupils are fundamental in every school, regardless of the disciplines taught. Teachers have a fundamental role and set of responsibilities to their students. TESOL has the primary role of placing a focus on students' linguistic growth and proficiency. Capabilities in these areas include reading, writing, grammar, listening, and speaking. The goal of education in the twenty-first century should be the development of each student's full potential, not only in terms of achieving success in studies but also in terms of leadership, service, and communication skills.

The English language is very influential around the globe. It has gained widespread recognition as a global language. (BB. Bohdanska, 2012) Educators and students are now more conscious of the necessity of learning English, which is being supported by most nations throughout the globe to close the gap in terms of political and economic relevance. Language proficiency in English is essential for effective communication on both the domestic and international levels. It's imperative that all people involved quickly become fluent in the language. The domains of business, technology, and science have all begun to fully use the English medium, which might boost their capabilities; therefore, it is impossible to deny that English has become equally significant in many sectors outside of education and language studies.

Notably, instructors in the Jhargram district of West Bengal confront several obstacles and problems from multilingual pupils in the classroom, making it difficult to accomplish the goal of teaching proficient English language communication. Students are unwilling and unable of communicating effectively in English. The mother-tongue conflict may be a significant issue. They're non-native speakers. The study's goals are to identify the strategies for using CLT to enhance learners' communication skills and to evaluate the efficacy of using CLT in Jhargram area of West Bengal.

Literature Review:

CLT is based on a set of principles that combine a variety of strategies and objectives aimed at enhancing the communicative skills of pupils. It emphasises the four abilities to make students independent in English speaking. CLT is a student-centered approach. The characteristics of CLT include classroom objectives which emphasises on all of the disciplines (sociolinguistic, grammatical, functional discourse, and strategy) of communicative skills. (Brown, 2000) A person's native language is not necessary for acquiring a second language and may potentially hinder that process. (Michael Swan, 2008) Introduced in ESL contexts, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) may make up for what was lacking in more conventional approaches of language instruction. (Littlewood (2007) Teaching and learning become alive in a CLT classroom because of the activities and interactions between instructors and students (Khoà Anh Viet, 2008). Students may also use textbook exercises and online roleplaying sites. (Doan Linh Chi, 2011)The role-play, simulations Discussions, , information gaps, storytelling , interviews, brainstorming, narrative completion, playing cards, reporting, image describing, and image narrating are just a few of the frequent speaking activities described. Students may develop their communication abilities via formal discourse. For instance, a structured interview may teach students how to engage in a question-and-answer session while addressing a preset set of topics and sharing specific facts. Students may improve their public speaking skills in a variety of contexts, including: the classroom, the outdoors, at home with friends, in speaking activities like theatre and debate, and in front of a mirror. Common classroom activities in a CLT environment include information-laps exercises,

jigsaw tasks, debate and discussion, communication games, and pre-planned lectures and verbal presentations. (Tuan and Mai, 2015) Thus, as predicted by the above mentioned intellectuals this study is going to focus on the implementation of CLT in ESL class room of Jhargram district of West Bengal.

Objectives, Research Questions and Hypothesis:

It is very common issues for Bengali and other vernacular medium schools to struggle with English language proficiency. This study will identify the following factors in order to alleviate this typical student nightmare:

- To evaluate how CLT affects ESL classrooms.
- To see the impact of CLT newly taught vocabulary in fluent speaking skills.
- To see whether the CLT technique really makes the class interactive or not.

The study's author hypothesised that CLT had a significant influence on vocabulary acquisition, making it simpler for students to acquire a command of Standard English pronunciation and diction.

Research Method

A quasi-experimental method was used in conducting this investigation with the pupils. This study aims to assess the efficacy of CLT by comparing results before and after exposure to the treatment. Stratified random sampling was used for this study's data collection. The researcher employed both quantitative and qualitative methods of analysis, dividing participants into two groups “control group” and an “experimental group” among the students of secondary schools in Jhargram district West Bengal. The quantitative method utilised in this study consists of a series of pre and post-tests. In addition to this method, a qualitative approach will be used in the research by interviewing and observing both students and teachers during the course of the study. Teachers' post-lesson thoughts were analysed.

Data Collection:

The researcher kept an open eye observation on students' linguistic skills as they worked through the in-class intervention. Over the course of four weeks, four trained English teachers taught 45-minute classes to the concern experimental group. At the conclusion of the concern course, an interview was arranged for both educators and learners to compare their observations of communicative language teaching to those of a control group. For pupils to demonstrate improvement, the post-test replicated the same set of questions and activities as the pre-test. There were 40 total participants in the study, 20 in each group chosen from secondary schools in Jhargram district West Bengal. Both exams had 20

multiple-choice questions 10 questions for each, and in addition to student responses, instructor comments will be taken into account.

Data Analysis:

Pre – Test Questionnaire Frequency Test in SPSS

After analysing the obtained score data, the researcher plans to do an SPSS frequency analysis on the responses to the questionnaire. In the pre-test, we asked the participant the questions listed below. In the table below, you'll see how the respondents answered the survey.

The post-test questionnaire frequency test shows that most of the respondent were agree and strongly agree that the present teaching method(GTM) is not adequate enough to

Post – Test Questionnaire Frequency Test in SPSS

After analysing the obtained score data, the researcher plans to do an SPSS frequency analysis on the responses to the questionnaire. In the post-test, we asked the participant the questions listed below. In the table below, you'll see how the respondents answered the survey.

****Note -1.00 – Strongly Disagree, 2.00 – Disagree, 3.00 – Neutral, 4.00 – Agree, 5.00 - Strongly Agree.**

The post-test questionnaire frequency test shows that most of the respondent were agree that CLT approach is enjoyable, it helps learners to learn English faster. The survey also denotes that CLT helps learners to occupy more new vocabulary and increase comprehensive power that inspired them to play the interactive role in the classrooms.

Mean and standard deviation scores were determined using both the pre- and post-test data for the learners' ability to speak orally. Then, we employed a paired sample t-test to make comparison between the pre- and post-learning speaking skills of the students with the aid of communicative activities by calculating the mean value and standard deviations of the tests. IBM SPSS 25 was used to analyse the data. The following numbers will give readers a clearer idea of the gap in performance that exists between the two concern groups “control group and the experimental group”.

As per the present table researcher had done frequency analysis between control group and experimental group which is given the table below :(Date Sheet Available in Annexure – 1).

Table 1*Statistics*

		CGPRE			EGPRE		
		NAME	T	CGPOT	NAME2	T	EGPOT
N	Valid	<u>20</u>	<u>20</u>	<u>20</u>	<u>20</u>	<u>20</u>	<u>20</u>
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		54.9500	57.4000		55.9500	67.7000	
Median		55.0000	56.0000	56.5000	68.5000	Std. Deviation	3.50150 3.61867 3.99309
Minimum		50.00	53.00	50.00	61.00		
Maximum		61.00	65.00	62.00	78.00		

Table 2*Paired Samples Statistics*

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	CGPO	57.40	20	3.61867	.80916
	T				
	CGPR	54.95	20	3.50150	.78296
	ET				
Pair 2	EGPO	67.70	20	4.73620	1.05905
	R				
	EGPR	55.95	20	3.99309	.89288
	ET				

The results shown in the tables show that there was a 10.30-point disparity in the mean post-test number between the two groups and a 1.11753-point difference in the standard deviations. When looking at the mean disparity between the concerned two groups, we observe that the experimental group improved their speaking abilities by 11.75 points thanks to the application of CLT, whereas the control group improved their skills by just 2.45 points.

Table 3*Paired Samples Correlations*

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair -1	CGPOT & CGPRET	20	.965	.000
Pair 2	EGPOR & EGPRET	20	.892	.000

Table 4*Paired Samples Test*

Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference					
				Lower	Upper				
Pair 1	CGPO T - CGPRET	2.4500	0.94451	0.21120	2.0079	2.89205	11.600	19	0.000
Pair 2	EGPO R - EGPRET	11.750	2.14905	0.48054	10.74421	12.75579	24.452	19	0.000

Note: CGPRET – Control Group Pre-Test, CGPOT- Control Group Post-Test, EGPRET- Experimental Group Pretest, EGPO- Experimental Group Post-Test.

The Paired Samples Test tables demonstrate that there was a disparity in the control group's standard deviations of 0.21120 points and a mean post-test score disparity between the concern two groups of 10.30 points. The experimental group's standard deviations differed by .48054 points. When comparing the two groups' means, we can see that the experimental group's speaking abilities increased by 11.75 points due to CLT, but the control group's speaking abilities increased by only 2.45 points. The paired sample table shows a substantial connection between the CLT and the speaking ability; the sig. value is 0.00, > than 0.005.

Table 5
Regression Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.893 ^a	.797	.773	2.25662

a. Predictors: (Constant), EGPRET, CGPRET

The R-square value is 0.797, which is shown in Table No. 5. This means that the independent variable, CLT (EGPRET, CGPRET), has a 79.70% effect on the dependent variable, speaking skills (EGPOT).

Table 6
ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	339.630	2	169.815	33.34	.000 ^b
	Residual	86.570	17	5.092		
	Total	426.200	19			

a. Dependent Variable: EGPOR

b. Predictors: (Constant), EGPRET, CGPRET

Table 6 displays a sig.-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, indicating that there is a substantial connection between the independent variable CLT (EGPRET, CGPRET) and the dependent variable speaking skills (EGPOT).

Table 7

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficient s		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Consta nt)	9.589	9.905		.968		.347
	CGPRE T	-.025	.151	-.019	-.166		.870
	EGPRE T	1.063	.133	.896	8.011		.000

a. Dependent Variable: EGPOR

Table 7 displays the coefficient results, which indicate that the control group's beta value is -.019, indicating that the group's post-test results have not changed significantly. However, the experimental group's beta value is .896, indicating that the experimental group's post-test results have changed significantly. This suggests that CLT has a substantial influence in the improvement of ESL students' English-speaking abilities.

The Research Results and Findings

There was a substantive improvement in learners' mean speaking scores between the pre- and post-tests. The paired sample t-test revealed that there is a substantial disparity between the means total of each group, with the experimental group having a larger number of differences than the control group. For this reason, using the 95% confidence interval is very necessary. This indicates that if the experiment were to be performed 100 times, the true value of the difference would be within the stated percentage 95 times out of 100. The P-value for this result has always been less than 0.05. These results provide more evidence that the disparities in grades are statistically substantial. The research findings are more evident enough to determine how both instructors and students perceive CLT's use in the ESL lecture theatre and its potential to develop students' oral communication abilities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The Results from the qualitative data analysis performed during the interview session with the sample teachers are summarise below. Students were found to be more interested in learning English for communicative reasons, and it was concluded that there was a high motivation for students to study English. Teachers were firm in their conviction that

students will adopt their teachers' perspective on language in the lecture theatre. It was also shown that initially, students would not speak English in class unless teachers strictly enforced the usage of just English, but after applying the CLT method, they became more interested in speaking without any hesitation. Teachers are also interested in CLT because it helps students improve their communication skills in a interesting and interactive way.

Faculties also welcomed the independence and usage of CLT in the ESL classroom to promote students' creativity via English learning and create a space for educators to adopt and alter some of the actions to incorporate communicative performance. The study suggests using thinking skills to adopt CLT, which encourages students to analyse and build topic-based conversations. Moreover, learners were noticed to engage in joint collaborative work and joint work during a week. It was interesting to perform among classmates in the class. However, the cardinal barrier for learners was the emphasis on other main skills such grammar, reading, and writing which are significant for the examination may discourage the emphasis on the communicative skills. It would be beneficial to do an additional study to assess the usefulness of the CLT in boosting public speaking abilities. Additionally, it would be profitable for other researchers to investigate the other new dimensions.

REFERENCES:

1. Kothari, C. R. (n.d.). *Methods and Techniques. (2nd Revised Ed.)*. New Delhi.
2. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2017). *Approaches and methods in language teaching create eBook (2nd ed.)*. Cambridge University Press.
3. Brown, H. D. (2000). *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching (4thed)*. Longman.
 <i>Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach Language Pedagogy(2nded)</i>. (2001). Longman.
4. Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2017). *Research methods in education (8th ed.)*. London, England: Routledge.
5. Brown, H. Douglas. (2015). *Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy etext (4th ed.)*. Philadelphia, PA: Pearson Education.
6. Cameron, L. (2011). *Cambridge language teaching library: Teaching languages to young learners*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
7. El-Koumy, A. S. A. (2004). *Teaching and Learning English as A Foreign Language: A Comprehensive Approach. USA: Educational Resources Information*

Center. ERIC.

8. Fraenkel, J., Wallen, N., & Hyun, H. (2022). *ISE how to design and evaluate research in education* (11th ed.). Columbus, OH: McGraw-Hill Education.
9. Matthew J. Davies (2011). Increasing students' L2 usage: An analysis of teacher talk time and student talk time. University of Birmingham. Retrieved from <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/Documents/collegeartslaw/cels/essays/languageaching/Daviesessay1TTTessaybank.pdf>
10. Matthew J. Davies (2011). Increasing students' L2 usage: An analysis of teacher talk time and student talk time. University of Birmingham. Retrieved from <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/Documents/collegeartslaw/cels/essays/languageaching/Daviesessay1TTTessaybank.pdf>
11. Kayi, H. (2006). Teaching speaking: Activities to promote speaking in a second language. The Internet TESL Journal, 7(11). Retrieved from <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Kayi-Teaching Speaking.html>
12. Khoa Anh Viet (2008). Imperialism of communicative language teaching and possible resistance against it from teachers in Vietnam as an English foreign languages context. VNU Journal of Science, Foreign Languages 24 (2008) 167-174.
13. Littlewood, W. (2007). Communicative and task-based language teaching in East Asian classrooms. Language Teaching 40 (3), 243-249.
14. Bc. BARBORA BOHDANSKÁ (2012). The level of knowledge of the cultural background of English-speaking countries among students of English language at a secondary school. UNIVERZITA PALACKÉHO V OLOMOUCI. Retrieved from https://theses.cz/id/9zhwj8/b_bohdanska.pdf
15. Brown, H. D. (2000). Principles of language learning and teaching (4th ed.). New York, NY: Longman.
16. Brown, H. D. (2001). Teaching by principles: An Interactive Approach Language Pedagogy (2nd ed.). San Francisco: Longman.
17. Cohen, L. (2013). Research methods in Education (7th ed). New York, NY: Routledge.
18. Tuan, N.H., & Mai, T.N. (2015). Factors Affecting Students' Speaking Performance at LE Thanh High School. Asian Journal of Educational Research Vol. 3 No.2.

19. Creswell, J. W. (2012). Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research(4th edition).USA: Pearson.
20. 55 Curtain, H., & Dahlberg, C. A. (2010). Language and children: Making the match, new language for young learners, grade K-8,4/E. Massachusetts, MA: Allyn& Bacon.
21. Ersoz, A. (2007). Teaching English to young learners. Ankara, Turkey: EDM Publishing.
22. Fathurrohman, M. (2015). Model-model pembelajaran inovatif. Yogyakarta, Indonesia: Ar-ruzz Media.

Annexure 1
Marks Table

Control Group				Experimental Group			
SL NO	Students Initials	Pre-Test Marks	Post-test Marks	SL NO	Students Initials	Pre-Test Marks	Post-test Marks
1.	P D	55.00	58.00	1.	PM	51.00	62.00
2.	A K	53.00	55.00	2.	PG	58.00	69.00
3.	S D	51.00	56.00	3.	FS	53.00	65.00
4.	BG	56.00	59.00	4.	HM	59.00	78.00
5.	PP	61.00	63.00	5.	SK	60.00	69.00
6.	KB	61.00	65.00	6.	BKP	56.00	68.00
7.	BP	55.00	56.00	7.	ASB	50.00	61.00
8.	PT	55.00	56.00	8.	AKM	57.00	69.00
9.	SG	61.00	63.00	9.	SCJ	58.00	69.00
10.	BM	54.00	56.00	10.	BL	60.00	71.00
11.	CM	52.00	54.00	11.	BV	55.00	63.00
12.	BT	51.00	53.00	12.	ML	62.00	75.00
13.	MKC	52.00	55.00	13.	BP	53.00	64.00
14.	DG	56.00	59.00	14.	AD	51.00	63.00
15.	PS	50.00	53.00	15.	AP	57.00	70.00
16.	BD	56.00	58.00	16.	SH	53.00	64.00
17.	CB	60.00	63.00	17.	ST	61.00	74.00
18.	SA	55.00	57.00	18.	PKD	52.00	65.00
19.	DKP	51.00	53.00	19.	SKM	51.00	63.00
20.	SH	54.00	56.00	20.	NKL	62.00	72.00